

CONCEPT OF POVERTY IN DIFFERENT SYSTEMATIC LANGUAGES

Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi

Termez state pedagogical institute, teacher

muattar9594@mail.ru

Abstract: The article provides an analytic evaluation of scientific works devoted to a specific thematic study in cognitive and cultural linguistics, the concept of "poverty," which is included in the corpus of basic ideas of numerous systematic languages. The article is made up of the systematization of the bulk of known scientific results of verbal representation, as well as the structuring of the concept of "poverty" in the contexts of English and Uzbek.

Keywords: concept, poverty, money, language representation, national language, culture, systematic languages.

Introduction.

Concepts appear within this theory in two domains: — in the domain of semantic form as the conceptual content of a lexical expression — in the domain of conceptual structure in terms of which the actual Interpretation of a given linguistic expression is specified. The domain of semantic form is related to the language-dependent representation of a conceptual structure, the conceptual structure is related to the universal representation of encyclopedic background knowledge, contextual Information and situational conditions. The semantic form of a lexical expression constitutes its core meaning, that is, the context-free meaning as stored in long term memory. The domain of conceptual structure is needed for the Interpretation of a given lexical expression in a certain context and Situation. The focus of two-level-semantics is upon the representational aspect of meaning as well as on the dynamic procedural aspect of Information processing. This kind of semantics is therefore claimed to be a part of cognitive Science and the cognitive information processing System does not necessarily have to be a human being. The distinction between semantic form and conceptual structure is mainly motivated by the overall phenomenon of the underdetermination of linguistic expressions. Well known examples are the following (cf. Bierwisch/Schreuder 1992; Schwarz 1992). Another group of word meanings can well be described by components, but they have another Organization and logical status than meaning postulates. This is the case with words like elephant, tiger, lemon, water and so on, so-called natural kind terms. Most Speakers of English are able to say what an elephant is, they have seen

an elephant in the zoo, or a picture of one, and they know something about the nature of the animal. Yet the term is a theoretical one (cf. Johnson Laird 1987, 203.)

Materials and methods

There are two basic ways to interpreting the "concept" in current linguistics: linguocognitive and linguo-cultural. The linguo-cognitive approach's proponents (I. A. Sternin, S. S. Kubriakova, D. S. Likhachev, P. Babushkin, S. Askoldov, and others.) define it as a mental formation that aids in the creation of a linguistic world image.

Linguo-cultural trend scientists (Wierzbicka, V. I. Karasik, U. S. Stepanov, S. G. Vorkachev, N. D. Arutyunova, U. S. Stepanov, S. K. H. Liapin, and others) regard the concept as a fundamental cultural unit, its focus.

Results and discussions.

Poverty is defined by the culture of learning in many organized languages. The words poverty and wealth are antonyms. Wealth must imply a complete existence, whereas poverty means powerlessness and a lack of resources. For example: Rich men have no faults. Money is an essential component of the economy. It is regarded as a replacement for respect and has damaged the beauty of relationships. It has become a societal trend to prioritize financial interests over moral virtues. Money has evolved into a social status symbol. Having a social status suggests that one is immune to having a flaw. It is because a wealthy individual has all of the means to live an extraordinary life. Money is considered to be a powerful tool for concealing flaws. Being a wealthy man imparts a sense of respectability. The authority and law-enforcement institutions also salute the wealthy. An environment might vary depending on the social structure and infrastructure.

“Work is the medicine for poverty” this means poverty is defined as a situation or circumstance in which people or communities lack the financial resources and necessities for a basic level of living. As a result, their basic human needs are unsatisfied. People and families living in poverty may lack adequate housing, clean water, nutritious food, and medical care. Each country may have its own set of criteria for identifying the poverty line and calculating how many people live in poverty. Poverty is a socioeconomic state caused by a variety of causes other than wealth. These characteristics include, among others, color, sexual identity, sexual orientation, and limited or no access to education.

Conclusion

Poverty is defined as a lack of enough financial resources, such that people, households, and entire communities lack the ability to subsist or purchase the

basic essentials of life. This is being so poor that you have to work hard to get food, clothing, shelter, and medicines. Poverty is both an individual concern and a bigger social one. Individual or household inability to make ends meet can result in a variety of physical and emotional difficulties. At the societal level, high poverty rates can stifle economic progress and be linked to issues such as crime, unemployment, urban deterioration, education, and bad health.

References

1. Bierwisch, M. & R. Schreuder (1992): FYom concepts to lexical items. In: *Cognition* 42, 23-60
2. Johnson-Laird, P.N: (1987): The mental representation of the meaning of words. In: *Cognition* 25, 189-211.
3. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi. (2023). The Role of Concept in Linguistics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(10), 50–53. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJRCS/article/view/1861>
4. Ibragimova Hilola Bahodirjon Qizi, & To'lqinova Maftuna Hasan qizi. (2023). DEBATE TECHNOLOGY AS AN INTERACTIVE FORM OF TEARNING IN ENGLISH CLASSES. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 2(4), 56–59. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/966>
5. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi. (2023). TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL TERMS. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology and Management*, 2(4), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7796602>
6. Qulmamatova Muattar Otabek qizi, Safarova Farida Normurotovna (2021). The Features of a Good Translator in Translating Medical Terms. *Analytical journal of education and development*, (2181-2624) <https://www.sciencebox.uz/index.php/ajed/article/view/526/505>
7. Сафарова, Д. А. (2018). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТОПОНИМОВ В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКИХ ЯЗЫКАХ. *Гуманитарный трактат*, (37), 26-27.
8. Akhmedova Adolat Ravshan kizi. (2022). Problems of Formation of Phonetic Competence of Students (A Level 1). *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 6, 160–162. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh/article/view/919>

9. Soatmurodova Shoxista Zafar qizi. (2023). ANALYSIS OF THE BORROWINGS RELATED TO THE FIELD OF “ATTAR” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 95–97. Retrieved from <https://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/966>
10. Ibragimova, H. B. qizi. (2022). INGLIZ TILINI O’QITISHDA PODKASTLAR VA ULARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AMALIY JIHATLARI. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*, 1(8), 212–219. Retrieved from <http://academics.uz/index.php/rnsr/article/view/1118>
11. Yadigarova Sitara Bahramovna. (2023). Analysis of Clothing Component Proverbs in English and Uzbek . *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(10), 353–356. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/2017>
12. Safarova Dilarom Abdukadirovna. (2023). THE PROPER NOUNS IN THE LEXICO-SEMANTICAL SYSTEM OF THE LANGUAGE. *American Journal of Philological Sciences*, 3(11), 29–31. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume03Issue11-05>
13. Nuriddinova, H. (2023). TOPISHMOQLAR TASNIFINING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 124-128.
14. Nuriddinova, H. (2023). TOPISHMOQLAR TASNIFINING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 124-128. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10409158>
15. Nuriddinova Hurriyat Bakhtiyarovna. (2021). CULTURE IS AN INSEPARABLE PART OF ANY ETHNIC GROUP. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(11), 120–126. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/P54EB>
16. KHUDAYBERDIEVICH M.M. (2023). The Concepts of Text and Discourse in Linguistics. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED LINGUISTIC STUDIES*.
17. Mukumov Makhmud Khudayberdievich. (2023). A BRIEF INSIGHT INTO INTERTEXTUALITY. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 414–420. Retrieved from <http://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/1099>